

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.1

Dissemination and Communication Plan

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Coordination and Support Action (2014-2020) under grant agreement No. 101021669

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable reference number	D6.1
Deliverable name	Dissemination and Communication Plan
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Work package contributing to the deliverable	WP6
Due date	31.10.2021 (M6)
Version	1.0
Actual submission date	08.11.2021

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Reviewers(s)	Steven Ormston, Rashel Talukder

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DOCUMENT CHANGE CONTROL

Version	Date	Status	Author(s), reviewer	Description
0.1	15/9/2021	Draft	Artmir Galica	Start of initial draft
0.2	31/10/2021	Draft	Artmir Galica	First draft ready

0.3	01/11/2021	Draft	Steven Ormston	Review
0.4	05/11/2021	Draft	Rashel Talukder	Review
0.5	05/11/2021	Draft	Artmir Galica	Final draft
1.0	08/11/2021	Final	Rashel Talukder	Final approval and submission

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1 Introduction

This document is part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation work package - WP6. The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DC – Deliverable (D) 6.1) is introducing the overall engagement approach that CYCLOPES will follow and respect for 60 months and beyond.

The DC Plan ensures efficient internal and external communications, as well as proper dissemination activities. The detailed plan recognises a variety of audiences and their respective needs and special interests. This is to ensure that the targeted audiences will be apprised of the most pertinent results stemming from the project.

To realise maximum benefits from the project's achievements, audiences will be encouraged to be actively involved with the project itself. This plan will describe the **means** and the **key messages** necessary to approach relevant stakeholders in an appropriate way, as well as how to maintain continuity of the relationship between them and the CYCLOPES consortium.

The DC Plan will be updated periodically (every 1.5 years) after its creation. The follow up of the DC Plan will track dissemination progress and provide additional direction and clarification to the activities according to the identified needs. Communication and dissemination activities will also be efficiently linked with exploitation activities of the project and the DC Plan will be updated together with the Exploitation Plan (EP).

Furthermore, this deliverable will ensure that:

- Project outputs and outcomes are widely disseminated to the right target audiences, respecting an appropriate and defined timing, through intelligible channels and tools,
- Stakeholders can contribute to the outputs development, evaluation and exploitation. Thus, they should be identified and encouraged from the start to proactively interact with the consortium partners on a systematic basis.

Given that the CYCLOPES project is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project, and considering the fact that the project will produce mainly practitioners' gaps and requirements reports and other deliverables that are highly useful for Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) in fighting against cybercriminals. It is clear that there will be confidential reports produced only for the use of the consortium partners and relevant EU bodies and actors. Therefore, the CYCLOPES team will also provide condensed – redacted versions of certain reports to support the active dissemination within the wider community.

The project dissemination will focus on network extension and sharing of the results internally and among the identified stakeholders and audience of interest. Thus the project will first require an understandable stakeholders' engagement approach - a key point of the DC. Furthermore, CYCLOPES intends to amplify the results and activities of other members of the cybercrime ecosystem – helping to maximise impact and positive change in the fight against different forms of cybercrime.

The primary step of knowing what has to be reached and understand why it must be reached, helps with the implementation of the engagement process in a significant way. These efforts define the appropriate messages for the relevant stakeholders, selects adequate tools and uses suitable channels, respecting a defined timing.

The Key audiences for CYCLOPES, as described in the proposal documents are:

- Practitioners,
- Industry including SMEs,
- Scientific Community,
- Policy makers

The strategy will also include key messages and means of approaching the aforementioned stakeholders.

This document includes the following sections:

1. The first section indicates general initial dissemination and communication objectives.
2. The second section analyses dissemination and communication objectives.
3. The third section analyses engagement of the audiences in the cybercrime domain.
4. The fourth section focuses on identifying the target audiences.
5. The fifth section dwells into the key messages based on the output/input from/to the project.
6. The sixth section outlines the dissemination tools.
7. The seventh section presents the project communication strategy.
8. The eighth section provides KPIs on monitoring and assessment of the D&C.

2 Dissemination and Communication Objectives

In addition to the most common communication and dissemination activities such as the project web page, social media channels, policy briefs, newsletters, reports and so on, the D&C will be attained through use of following dissemination methods:

- participate in dozens of events dedicated to practitioners, industry and research – presenting the project’s outcomes and encouraging exploitation of the results;
- directly share outcomes with identified EU projects developing tools and solutions for practitioners fighting cybercrime;
- develop bi-annual reports for the European Commission about CYCLOPES findings;
- annual reports for policymakers on European and national level, with recommendations of research areas which should be financed in the future;
- annual CYCLOPES dissemination workshops.

In terms of a specific methodological approach, the CYCLOPES project will employ a methodology, which provides a 360-degree or continuous cycle approach consisting of planning, performing, assessing, and reporting (Figure 1).

Figure 1. CYCLOPES D&C, 360 degree - continuous cycle approach.

The CYCLOPES project comprehends the importance of communicating its project results, and for this reason, it will implement thorough internal and external communication and dissemination activities.

The objectives for **CYCLOPES external communications and dissemination** are to:

- Ensure efficient dissemination of project results.
- Create project visibility.
- Reach various target groups (please refer to the following section 4).
- Guarantee sustainability of the project results (implemented through the Communication and Dissemination strategy).
- Increase the awareness about both the topic of cybercrime and cybersecurity and specific purposes and actions linked to the project.

- Involve the whole community in a participatory communication plan structured in various steps.

The objectives for **CYCLOPES internal communication and dissemination** are to:

- Monitor the status of CYCLOPES developments to keep WPs aware of the project progress.
- Ensure coherent internal communication between WPs.
- Make relevant internal information available also to external communication.
- Ensure an efficient and smooth communication among partners.
- Allow and enable the sharing of interesting and relevant content for the project.

D6.1 will address the relevant stakeholders through several identified channels, which include the following:

- Social networks (Twitter and LinkedIn);
- Website;
- Podcasts on the internet;
- Webinars;
- Use of following information sharing platforms by partners (all or a select few):
 - Community of Users EC Platform,
 - Stashcat application,
 - i-LEAnet project's platform,
 - iProcureNet project's platform,
 - CMINE Platform,
 - Stair4Security project's platform and so on
 - Europol's Platform for Experts
- Promotion of open science with selected public information, published in EC platforms such as:
 - [Open Research Europe](#),
 - [European Open Science Cloud](#),
 - [CORDIS](#),
 - [EC Horizon Results Platform](#),
 - [EC Horizon Results Booster](#) and so on;
- Workshops and Exercises;
- Consortium partners' own networks;
- CYCLOPES' network members.

The above mentioned tools and platforms are a few steps that the project will incorporate in the activities to maximise its impact. More on those will follow in the sections below.

Furthermore, as technology develops we need to take into account that there is a general noise of information that floods audiences' daily activities. To maximise the effectiveness of communications, some of the CYCLOPES D&C activities should focus on short, concise, to the point communications strategy when it comes to sharing information. Such strategy could be beneficial when it comes to: newsletters, podcasts, social media publishing and so on.

Given that the project is a coordination and support action, this could also be a limiting factor to some degree due to the intended audience being specific. Nevertheless, the follow up of the DC Plan will track dissemination progress and provide additional direction and clarification to the activities according to the identified needs. Furthermore, communication and dissemination

activities will be efficiently linked with exploitation activities of the project and the DC Plan will be updated together with the Exploitation Plan (EP). Figure 1.

3 Engaging with targeted audiences in the cybercrime & cybersecurity domain

3.1 Objectives for engaging

Efficient dissemination during the CYCLOPES project ensures short and long-term success of the project. In any research or coordination project, the dissemination is a fundamental activity to create project visibility and reach various target groups. This is core to the strategy of spreading knowledge about the project among different target groups by using different instruments.

Understanding the reasoning behind stakeholders' engagement is the first step for a well-defined engagement strategy; including the selection of appropriate tools to be used.

Below are five main objectives for engaging CYCLOPES stakeholders:

Extend and enhance CYCLOPES' reputation: communicating about CYCLOPES' aim, objectives and work that is dedicated to cybercrime prevention will improve its image and gain stakeholders' trust;

Extend the network and cooperation between LEAs in the cybercrime and cybersecurity domain.

Gather information about CYCLOPES stakeholders' needs and requirements.

Boost awareness of CYCLOPES' objectives and outcomes at local, national, European and international levels;

Intensify CYCLOPES' impact: efficient and personalised communication with stakeholders will support the uptake of the project's outcomes and increase their relevance;

3.2 Level of engagement

Like other EU funded projects, CYCLOPES will follow the Spectrum of Public Participation which has been developed by the [International Association of Public Participation](#), which is to:

Inform: to provide the CYCLOPES communities with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities, and/or solutions;

Consult: obtain feedback on analysis, alternatives, and/or decisions;

Engage: work directly with the community members throughout the project and beyond to ensure that practitioners' concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered;

Collaborate: partner with the CYCLOPES community members in each aspect of the decision-making process - including the development of alternative options and the identification of the preferred 'solutions';

Empower: Place final decision-making authority in the hands of the CYCLOPES community

members.

More detailed information on how the project CYCLOPES plans to adopt the above methodology can be found on the WP5's deliverable D5.1. *Community Building Framework and Governance model*. For this deliverable we will mainly focus on the dissemination perspective.

4 Identified stakeholders and target groups

To maximise the engagement of the stakeholders, the key point is to clearly define the categories of stakeholders, their needs and the priority group they belong.

In this document we are mainly focusing on identification of target groups and their needs for dissemination purposes in order not to duplicate efforts with WP5. WP5 will delve more into detail on the stakeholder engagement activities.

By engaging key stakeholders from the start of the project, CYCLOPES will acquire a more motivated and interested participant base and will allow early opportunities for dissemination communication and exploitation. In addition, the targeted and timely communication will allow the different target groups to be informed about and participate in the various events planned in the project

When it comes to the identified stakeholders, the planning stage consists of considering fundamental questions such as:

- Is there a need to disseminate and why?
- Who are the target audience?
- What is the content that is being disseminated?
- Who is completing the dissemination?
- When is dissemination taking place?
- How will it be disseminated?

The key stakeholders as defined in the project proposal are divided into four main categories (Figure 2):

Figure 2 CYCLOPES Stakeholder Audiences

4.1 Practitioners

With practitioners in the context of CYCLOPES project, it is referred to the Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs), interested in the uptake of security research and innovation in relation to the fight against cybercrime.

CYCLOPES partners will engage practitioners throughout the project timeframe by inviting relevant stakeholders to events and workshops, by proposing that they take part in different initiatives and ask for their feedback on how CYCLOPES solutions can support enhanced resilience to cybercrime.

CYCLOPES thus far has identified the following networks/practitioners. Some of the agencies mentioned below are not fully classified as LEAs however, the main target are the LEAs participating in those networks, plus the actions that are providing results and outputs utilised by LEAs – such as EACTDA and ECTEG.

As the CYCLOPES network increases to include more LEAs, the list will expand.

Table 1 List of targeted practitioner audience

Practitioners community	Target Audience	How to reach
<i>LEA full partners</i>	12 full project partners	
<i>Practitioners’ Forum</i>	Additional EU LEAs,	Proactively disseminate information related to the project, formal invitations to join the network via several planned channels.
<i>Practitioners’ Networks</i>	LEAs participating to the following networks: ENLETS, STARLIGHT, ENFSI, ECTEG, i-LEAD, CERIS, i-LeaNet, EU-HYBNET, ARCSAR, i-ProcureNet, POLARCLUSTER & POLARNET, Forensic Capability Network	Proactively disseminate information related to the project to increase visibility of project existence. Provide a project summary to include in their media. Distribute marketing materials. Extend formal invitations to join the network via several planned channels. Join their networks.
<i>EU / international orgs</i>	LEAs from the following: EC3, Interpol, CEPOL, Europol Innovation Hub, ENISA, EACTDA	Proactively disseminate information and reports related to the project. Provide a project summary to include in their media. Distribute marketing materials. Extend formal invitations to join the network via several planned channels. Join their networks.

4.2 Industry including SMEs

When it comes to the industry and SMEs, it is generally meant those whose activities are relevant to cybercrime/cybersecurity. This includes:

- Manufacturers
- Service providers
- Vendors
- Industry Associations
- Suppliers
- Industry Think Tanks

CYCLOPES project has a dedicated work package 3 to conduct the market and research watch, as well as WP5 that focuses on stakeholder engagement. Nevertheless all consortium members are expected to play a role in the engagement activities as well i.e. industry players with interests in cybercrime and work constructively with its wide network (security industry, suppliers of security solutions). It can be that some of the partners have own contacts or are members of other networks which they could invite to CYCLOPES activities, or at least make them known to the WP5 leader. This network will be invited to attend events, workshops and webinars of CYCLOPES and will receive all supportive documents needed to actively participate in key activities.

Certainly, the challenge to find and engage adequate industry SMEs with substantial interest to the project and willing to contribute, is recognized and the project should be selective in this regard. There is a multitude of SMEs, many of which are either dealing with specific niche clients or some are very limited based on their representation on their websites.

Nevertheless, in order for the project to maximize its reach to the industry, CYCLOPES consortium is encouraged to participate to events, conferences, networks, clusters, fairs and so on where the number of industry participants is high.

The following is a preliminary list of some of the potential Industry SMEs/networks that could be invited to contribute in CYCLOPES events. Worth to note that some of the SMEs chosen are coming from the project i-LEAD, where they were contributors to the project events.

Table 2 Preliminary list of targeted audience from the industry/SMEs

Industry community	Target Audience	How to reach
<i>Industry SME's</i>	All identified industry and SMEs	Proactively contact individual SME's to share project news and attract their interest to establish contacts and newsletter subscription as well as participate to CYCLOPES project events and vice versa.
Industry members of networks	Industry participating to the following networks: EUROPEAN Digital SME Alliance, NETWORLDEUROPE, ENFSI, ECTEG, i-LEAD, CERIS, EU-HYBNET, ARCSAR, i-ProcureNet	Proactively participate to events. Announce the project existence to the networks and include perhaps a short project bio in their website. Participate to the project clusters as well and show a badge of membership. Engage in social media and invite them to join to our events.
<i>EU / international orgs</i>	Industry/SMEs from the following: ECSO, CEEMET, SIINDA, UNIFE, Europol Innovation Hub, ENISA, SAFECLUSTER,	Proactively participate to events. Announce the project existence to the networks and include perhaps a short project bio in their website. Participate to the project clusters as well and show a badge of membership. Engage in social media and invite them to join to our events.

4.3 Scientific community

CYCLOPES results and updates will be delivered to relevant EU and Member State organisations. At the beginning of the project there are several scientific communities identified such as:

- Universities,
- Research and technology organisations,
- Research communities and institutes,
- The private sector.

Participation from this target group will be mutually beneficial. For CYCLOPES it means that an essential component in the development process is present in the project to contribute with experiences and input on feasibility of project results. To the researchers, it provides means of tapping into a vast repository of knowledge related to topics such as cyber-physical threats, emergency response, forensics, cybercrime, information systems and system resilience.

Table 3 Preliminary list of potential target for scientific communities.

Practitioners community	Target Audience	How to reach
<i>Scientific full CYCLOPES partners</i>	All	
<i>Scientific Forum</i>	All scientific forums identified	Proactively disseminate information related to the project, public reports, formal invitations to join project activities via several planned channels.
<i>Scientific' Networks</i>	Scientific members participating to the following networks: ENFSI, EU Research Gate ECTEG, i-LEAD, i-LeaNet, EU-HYBNET, ARCSAR, i-ProcureNet, POLARCLUSTER & POLARNET	Proactively disseminate information related to the project to increase visibility of project existence. Distribute marketing materials. Extend formal invitations to join the project activities via several planned channels.
<i>EU / international orgs</i>	Scientific communities from the following: Open Research Europe , European Open Science Cloud, Initiative for Science in Europe, Science Europe, EU Science Hub, CORDIS, EC Horizon Results Platform, EC Horizon Results Booster	Proactively disseminate information and public reports related to the project. Provide a project summary to include in their media. Distribute marketing materials. Extend formal invitations to participate to CYCLOPES activities via several planned channels. Join their networks.

4.4 Policymakers

Through policy-oriented partners, policy and decision makers will be approached. The CYCLOPES consortium will identify and proactively contact with targeted personnel and invite interested actors to project events and workshops. The relevant files under discussion will also be identified and their development monitored by the consortium.

CYCLOPES will reach policymakers on a **European** (i.e. DG Home, DG Connect, DG Grow) **National** level (member states).

These audiences are at the core of the main goals of the DC plan. Throughout the duration of the project, CYCLOPES intends to build and sustain efficient audience relations in order to enable interaction between differing innovation parties, and build synergies with already established European, national and sub-national networks of practitioners. Moreover, efficient

communication and dissemination measures, together with exploitation activities, are the key in fulfilling the goals of the Work Program.

Table 4 Preliminary list of potential target Policymakers

Practitioners community	Target Audience	How to reach
<i>Member State Level</i>	All project partners' national level policymakers. EU member national policymakers.	Proactively disseminate information related to the project, public reports, formal invitations to join project activities via several planned channels.
<i>EU /Global level</i>	DG HOME, DG CONNECT, DG GROW, DG MOVE, DG MARE, REA, EC, ENISA, CEN, CENELEC, ISO	Proactively disseminate project results. Extend formal invitations to participate to CYCLOPES activities via several planned channels. Join their networks.

4.5 Related projects and initiatives

There is also a fifth identified group which is the cooperation with other similar projects to facilitate synergies and sharing of project results and making use of project networks.

Related projects or initiatives are a crucial vector for the development of CYCLOPES. They are an important stakeholder category, as their environment needs to be aligned with CYCLOPES' approach, avoiding possible overlap and enhancing complementary synergies.

CYCLOPES will engage with a wide range of EU Projects and European and national activities, already identified during the preparation phase. In the following table there is an exemplification of the links already developed:

Table 5 List of EU projects and initiatives

EU PROJECTS		
Project Acronym	CYCLOPES partner	Field of Activities
i-LEAD, i-LEAnet, i-ProcureNet	PPHS, DITSS, HO, UCD CCI	identification of LEA needs, cybercrime, standardisation, procurement, market & research watch
ARCSAR	LAUREA	arctic security and emergency first response
EU-HYBNET	LAU, PPHS, ZITiS	hybrid threats, future trends, cyber and future technologies, innovation mapping and recommendations for standardisation
ASGARD, TITANIUM,	TNO, DITSS, HO, PPHS,	fight against crime and terrorism, establish new knowledge to explore the feasibility of a

ANITA, TRILLION, FORMOBILE, UNITY, PROPHETS, ROXANNE, MAGNETO, COPKIT	ASI, MUP, GDC OC	new or improved technology, product, process, service or solution
AIDA	CRI, CENTRIC	artificial intelligence data analysis
RESPOND-A	IANUS	next-generation equipment tools and mission- critical strategies for first responders
SPARTA, CONCORDIA, ECHO, SANCUS	PPHS, LAU, IANUS	cybersecurity, information security technologies, knowledge and technology transfer, competence hub for innovation
TENSOR	CRI, CENTRIC	terrorist activity recognition, data protection
FORESIGHT VISION	CRI, TNO, CENTRIC	improve cybersecurity, roadmap for the development of AI in Europe
GRACE	CRI, CENTRIC	bio-based industries joint technology initiative
ANDROMEDA	LAU	strengthen security through border management, information sharing for border command, control and coordination systems
SAFETY4 RAILS	LAU	data-based analysis for safety and security protection for detection, prevention, mitigation and response in trans-modal metro and railway networks
INFINITY	CENTRIC	Cybercrime, terrorists and hybrid threats
TRESPASS	TNO	training in secure and privacy-preserving biometrics, security protection
Stairs4Security	ASI	innovation and research for security, standardisation in the CBRNe sectors
BDVe	TNO	big data value ecosystem
DRIVER+	TNO	innovation in crisis management for European resilience
SIIP	MUP	audio and voice analysis, speaker identification for security applications
Lion DC	PPHS, DITSS, GDCOC	fight against online drug crimes
PRoTECT	DITSS	protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens, biometric identification, security and privacy standards
National Initiatives		
UK National Cyber Project	CENTRIC	cybercrime, cybersecurity
Cryptocurrency investigation SG	CENTRIC – Europol	cryptocurrency training game for law enforcement professionals
EU Strategy Documents		
Council of Europe Guidelines for LEA	CRI	Fighting against crime and terrorism (including cybercrime)

4.6 Stakeholders' needs

Stakeholders needs are crucial part in the project dissemination plan as we need to understand and plan for relevant information to be shared and selected stakeholders to be targeted based on different kinds of events. Figure 3 below illustrates the stakeholders' input/output to and of the project based on their needs identified.

Figure 3 stakeholders' input/output to and of the project based on their needs identified

4.6.1 Practitioners

Practitioners in the CYCLOPES project are a very specific stakeholder that includes only LEAs. It is easy for us to distinguish the needs of this group from the rest as they are mainly interested in the identification of the gaps, needs and capabilities in the cybercrime/cybersecurity area. Practitioners need to have access to all project reliable information and integrate them in their daily work. Their behaviour needs to be adapted to the state of security that they aim to reach.

Practitioners are in the epicentre of the CYCLOPES project as they comprise the network therefore they should be included in all project activities.

4.6.2 Industry Including SMEs

The Industry group can be divided into the following categories.

- Manufacturers need to be aware of current trends and threats related to cybercrime in order to be able to offer new innovative solutions that could help LEA's fighting cybercrime
- Service providers, have to be aware of the potential threats and risks associated with cybercrime/cybersecurity and propose/implement appropriate security solutions to prevent the risks and to mitigate the impact of some crisis and vulnerabilities.

- Vendors need to be aware of the trends and needs of the practitioners in order to make available new technologies for procurement by LEAs
- Industry Associations need to be aware of the CYCLOPES aims and create appropriate industry associations for example dedicated to cybercrime/cybersecurity
- The *suppliers* need guidance into the security requirements and examples of security solutions proven to be effective in the targeted context to improve the security provided by their products and services.
- Industry Think Tanks need guidance into trends and security requirements for uptake and creating trends in the market.

Security Industry needs insight into trends and risks that occur in the cybercrime domain. It also requires opportunities to validate novel security solutions in such eco-systems.

4.6.3 Scientific Community

CYCLOPES can be relevant for the scientific community concerning cybercrime in order to provide feedback on the feasibility, applicability in real life scenario of project results.

More specifically the idea would be to:

- Provide guidance in terms of the interpretation of requirements in scope,
- Exchange research results, in order to efficiently use available resources.

The results of such an action will be interesting for the scientific community also for other stakeholders that may access the relevant information.

4.6.4 Policymakers

Policymakers need to be aware of the project results in order to understand the requirements for innovation and further standardization and to be able to adequately include in the future policies new and innovative ways for LEAs to combat cybercrime while ensuring all are well within SEL frameworks. It is crucial for them to receive the correct information in order to act accordingly.

The integration of inputs coming from diverse stakeholders can also be used to support the implementation of related projects and initiatives.

4.6.5 Related projects and initiatives

Having cooperation with other projects and initiatives is crucial to ensure the CYCLOPES projects' successful implementation and relevancy. Similarly also the related projects must know what is happening in the CYCLOPES project via publications and other channels as described in the task 5.1 of the WP5.

A crucial part of this group is to synchronise work for example, if i-LEAD has one annual workshop dedicated to cybercrime, CYCLOPES must know which topics are planned for forthcoming workshops to avoid duplication of tasks. Same goes for the other initiatives and their relevant actions. CYCLOPES must ensure that proper engagement happens with this group in order to maximize impact and relevancy of work.

5 Key Messages

Throughout the project, dissemination and communication efforts will be developed in such a way that they will communicate the main messages the project intends to communicate between the identified target groups.

The messages will be selected carefully according to the needs of the stakeholders and the project activity in question. Mainly the messages will be created based on the following questions:

Whom are we targeting?

What is the need of the project activity and stakeholder (benefit)?

What needs to be disseminated (Message)?

Table 6 CYCLOPES objectives that can be used to direct messages to targeted audiences

	Practitioners	Industry Inc. SMEs	Policymakers	Scientific community	Related Projects and Initiatives
WP1 Project Management & Security Matters					
Objectives related to the Project Management and security matters					
Achieve Project objectives	To get access to the achievement of project Objectives	To get access to the opportunities to further improve project outputs	To gain a better understanding of the project for future influence on Policies	To get the opportunity to give feedback on project outputs	To get a better understanding of the project, enhance collaboration and avoid overlap
WP2 Identification of practitioners' capabilities, gaps and requirements					
Objectives related to practitioners' capabilities, gaps and requirements					
To identify Gaps, Needs & Capabilities	To be able to give feedback on the identification of Gaps, Needs and capabilities	To be able to suggest solutions to G, N & C	To have access to the G,N&S identified	To have access and give feedback to the G, N & C identified. Stimulate further research.	To be aware of the G, N & C identified and to facilitate synergies
To increase European Stakeholders' knowledge of the cybercrime threats	To get knowledge on Cybercrime threats	To get knowledge on cybercrime threats	To get knowledge on cybercrime threats	To get knowledge on cybercrime threats	To get knowledge on cybercrime threats
To test Innovation to enhance practitioners' measures	To be aware of the tests and give feedback on Innovation	To be aware of the test and to be able to take a position on	To be aware of the test as input for potential follow up	To be aware of the results of the tests	To be aware of the test

against cybercrime		the market and contribute to cybercrime needs	action when needed	and use them	
To support the extension of actors in the European Network against cybercrime	To be part of the European Network combating cybercrime		To support the network of LEAs combating cybercrime	To participate to the events of the project	To participate to the events of the project
WP3 Research, innovation and market watch					
Objectives related to research, innovation and market watch					
To map the needs for innovations.	To be aware of the mapping	To be aware of the mapping	To be aware of the mapping	To be aware of the mapping	To be aware of the mapping
To monitor and select available innovative solutions for measures against cybercrime threats	To contribute to the solution selection	To be aware of the selected solutions as input for potential follow up action when needed	To understand any policy-related points relevant to solutions selected	To contribute to the possible solutions	CYCLOPES to use potential project results to map innovations
To arrange joint exercises/events with detailed scenarios of cybercrime threats	To be aware of the events and attend them	To be aware of the events and attend them	To observe the events and gain understanding of the tech and how it impacts policy	To be aware of the events and attends them	To be aware of the events and attend them
WP4 Standardisation and innovation uptake					
Objectives of the standardisation and innovation uptake					
To identify priorities related to fighting cybercrime requiring standardisation	To support and be aware of the priorities requiring standardisation	To be aware of the standardisations and see its potential influence on the market via select public reports	To be aware of the standardisation requirements	To be aware of the standardisation requirement via select public reports	To be aware of the standardisation requirement via select public reports and uptake of results as input
To compile recommendations for	To support the compilation of most		To be aware of the recommendations as input	To be aware of the standardisation	To be aware of the standardisation

standardisation activities	critical G,N & C requiring standardisation		for potential follow up action when needed	ion requirement via select public reports	ion requirement via select public reports and uptake of results as input
To deliver Policy Briefs, Position Papers and Recommendations	To be aware of the documents and to participate in workshops	To be aware of the documents produced and to participate in events	To be aware of the documents produced as input for potential follow up action when needed, to participate in workshops	To be aware of the publications	To be aware of the publications for potential results uptake
WP5 CYCLOPES community building					
Objectives of CYCLOPES community building					
to establish, build and maintain cooperation with other practitioners, practitioner networks and other relevant stakeholders	To be aware of the existence of the network.	To be aware of the existence of the network.	To be aware of the existence of the network.	To be aware of the existence of the network.	To be aware of the existence of the network.
Extend the network of practitioners with new members	To join the network				
WP6 Communication, dissemination and exploitation					
Objectives of Communication, dissemination and exploitation					
To disseminate results and interact with other related networks	To be aware of the main results and objectives of CYCLOPES	To be aware of the results in order to take a position on the market	To be aware of the main results of CYCLOPES To have the opportunity to improve actual policy	To be aware of the main results of CYCLOPES	To be aware of the main results of CYCLOPES
To create conditions for better interaction with LEAs, industry, academia,	To be part of the CYCLOPES Network and have access to project resources	To be aware of the network existence and be able to find	To be aware of the network existence and be able to find relevant information	To be able to interact with the project in various channels.	To be able to interact with the project in various channels.

EC, EU agencies and member states. Support enriching existing network combating cybercrime with practitioners.	aimed at the network members.	relevant information			
WP7 Societal, Ethical and Legal Connections Related to Cybercrime					
Objectives related to Societal, Ethical and Legal Connections Related to Cybercrime					
analyse the potential and actual societal, ethical and legal (SEL) challenges related to cybercrime investigation activities	to be aware of potential societal and ethical issues related to cybercrime G,N&C and solutions as input and output	Be aware of opportunities and limitations that come from the SEL perspective towards new innovations	Be aware of opportunities and limitations that come from the SEL perspective towards new innovations and potential uptake of results	Be aware of opportunities and limitations that come from the SEL perspective towards new innovations in cybercrime	Be aware of opportunities and limitations that come from the SEL perspective towards cybercrime innovations
To provide clear forms throughout the project that take into consideration SEL issues	To be aware of limitations/opportunities of joining the network	To be aware of limitations/opportunities of providing input/output in/of the project taking into account SEL challenges		To be aware of limitations/opportunities of providing input/output in/of the project taking into account SEL challenges	To be aware of limitations/opportunities of providing input/output in/of the project taking into account SEL challenges
WP8 Ethics requirements					
Objectives related to Ethics Requirements are for administrative purposes.					
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

6 Dissemination tools

6.1 Online dissemination channels

Online dissemination tools play a key role in the overall project dissemination. The advantage of having an online presence is that it facilitates a quick way to reach targeted audiences and raise interest among the cybercrime threat community and the civil society in general.

6.1.1 Cyclopes Website

PPHS has created a dedicated CYCLOPES website (Figure 4), which serves as the primary channel to support communication and dissemination of project information and results. The

website maintains the same graphical identity as the other communication tools used within the project.

The website is accessible from desktop as well as mobile devices on the following address <https://cyclopes-project.eu>. It will host publicly available content produced by the project such as relevant upcoming events, news, public deliverables, project information, network information and so on.

Figure 4 CYCLOPES website

6.1.1.1 Design and Architecture

The current structure (Figure 5) might receive slight changes throughout the project as the project matures and more information and/or needs are identified.

Home page

Represents the landing page of the website and an overview of the project and navigation system for ease of access to project information (Figure 4).

Website Architecture

Figure 4 CYCLOPES website architecture

News

This section holds the latest blog news published by the project. It provides a way to quickly find the latest updates by the project. News will be published accordingly on need basis.

About

The about page is expected to hold information regarding the project CYCLOPES and what it stands for, objectives, network information, consortium, various boards information on work plan and so on.

Events

The events page will feature all upcoming and past events organised by the project such as workshops, live exercises and where the project participates. Events will also be featured in the news section.

Contact

The project website provides a form and contact information for general inquiries.

For LEAs

The page displays information that concerns LEAs mainly an introduction to the project objectives and how LEA's can contribute to the project. There is also a call to action to join the CYCLOPES network.

For Research & Industry

On this page, information aimed particularly at research and industry is provided in order to inform them about the project relevant information as well as ways they can contribute.

Downloads

This page will offer a way to list downloadable content that is produced by the project. This can be i.e. public deliverables, newsletters, press releases, event reports and so on.

Newsletter subscription

In addition to the current page sections, the CYCLOPES website also offers a way for the visitors to sign-up for the newsletter. The form can be located by scrolling down (footer area) and can be accessed throughout the website. This section is still in development at the time of writing the deliverable hence more updates will come later.

6.1.1.2 Security and Maintenance

For security reasons not a lot of detailed information can be disclosed with regards to technology, servers and security measures taken.

The C&D team will regularly review the website traffic and user behaviour to monitor security threats, and will keep the systems patched and upgraded when possible to ensure they are providing adequate protection.

6.1.1.3 GDPR Compliance

A link to the privacy policy will be provided as a pop-up banner to the users to read before accessing the website. This will inform the user of the data we gather, any tracking performed and the cookie policy. The user will have the choice to continue using the site under the set conditions or navigate away.

An agreement policy will be prepared and the visitors will be informed on the reasons the website collects any information and how this information will be used, as in the case with newsletter subscriptions, contact forms and registration to platforms.

Visitors will have the right to request to know the data the website holds about them and for its destruction upon request. However, some data of offensive nature i.e. deliberate hacking attempts may be held for security and forensic purposes.

6.1.2 CYCLOPES Private Areas

The main objective of the CYCLOPES private area, is to facilitate communication and exchange of knowledge with the members of the advisory boards, project partners and network members. The CYCLOPES workspace is created in the Microsoft TEAMS collaborative tool which is provided by the project coordinator PPHS.

This CYCLOPES workspace enables its members to:

- Share and stock documents
- Organise meetings
- Manage directories and contacts
- Discuss special issues
- Other general collaboration needs

To create solid working relations and to achieve the desired results of the CYCLOPES project, it is imperative that all partners work together and communicate freely. Internal communications are essential to establish a strong grasp of the project's vision, values and objectives. All members of the consortium should feel included and integrated with the efforts,

in all of the work packages. All-inclusive communication among all project partners and participants is critical for the PMO to follow and monitor the project progress. Moreover, it will boost team building and encourage individual accountability for the achieved results. The foundation for good communication is consistency. Therefore, a regular cadence for group meetings will be set. The following list forms the foundation for promoting good internal communications:

- Regular consortium meetings; at least once a year (General Assembly)
- Monthly online meetings
- WP team meetings through telephone or video conferences
- Quarterly coordination meetings (Project Board) through online meetings,
- Access to the on-line communication platform dedicated to the CYCLOPES project (Microsoft Teams);
- Regular contact between the Project Management Office, the WP Leaders and other contributors;
- Reports every EU reporting period.

6.1.3 Social media

As we have seen through experience, social media platforms offer a great opportunity to target desired audiences to keep them updated with project progress. Their simplicity in publishing content and their openness offer an easy way to reach audiences regardless of the device. The WP6 leader and the project coordinator have decided that for our specific project needs, LinkedIn and Twitter accounts would be more favourable as opposed to Facebook, Instagram and other platforms.

6.1.3.1 Twitter

A twitter account has been created for the CYCLOPES project called project-cyclopes. (Figure 6). The initial plan was to name the account cyclopes-project, the same as the website, however this at the time was unavailable. Another limiting factor was that the account name had to be comprised of no more than 15 characters. During a WP meeting held on September 2021, we decided to keep the current account names and not pursue the change as mentioned in the D6.11.

To support project activities, we will use the (@) mentions as well as (#) hashtags where appropriate, in order for our posts to be easily found by interested parties.

The current hashtags planned for use in CYCLOPES project communications. However, **on domain specific dissemination, it is recommended that at least the first two are used in combination with other relevant hashtags. I.e. #cyclopesnetwork #lawenforcement #digitalforensics and so on.** Similarly when targeting a specific organisation it is recommended to mention them either via hashtag (#) or tag (@).

- #cyclopesnetwork
- #cyclopesproject
- #cybercrime
- #cybersecurity

- #H2020

Figure 5 CYCLOPES Twitter account

6.1.3.2 LinkedIn

A LinkedIn account has also been created and named **project-cyclopes**. (Figure 7) (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/project-cyclopes/>). With the same vision in mind as the Twitter one, LinkedIn has been recognised as the best platform aimed at reaching professionals which allows posting longer content than Twitter. With that in mind we will use LinkedIn to promote network expansion and keep our followers updated with project news and materials. Here we also faced a similar issue of the name being already taken hence we kept the same name as the Twitter one. During a WP meeting held on September 2021, we decided to keep the current account names and not pursue the change as mentioned in the D6.11.

Figure 6 CYCLOPES LinkedIn account

6.1.4 Newsletter

Will include project updates and a call for contributions on project activities. It will describe achievements and upcoming activities, and will be shared amongst the partners and the CYCLOPES network. The newsletter will also be published on the project website, sent out to interested recipients, and made available on social media. The current plan for the newsletter is that it will be created twice a year to report on project progress. We will monitor the feasibility of creating a mini newsletter to be delivered more often. Implementation of this idea comes down to project resources.

6.1.5 Webinar

The webinars will be an additional opportunity to disseminate the project findings and increase the overall impact. At least one webinar will be organized per year throughout the project timeline. Topics for the webinars will be selected on the ongoing basis to ensure they are aligned with contemporary trends.

6.1.6 Materials for new network members

It should be foreseen that in order for the new network members to feel welcome to the CYCLOPES network, a few introductory/welcoming materials should be prepared and shared.

This would include at least:

- Welcoming message/paper,
- Welcoming and guidance package on the actions that come next

The documents will be discussed with the WP5 leader and agree on the best approach.

6.1.7 Publications, press releases, articles

Consortium members, partners and external entities will collaborate on joint publications. Press releases and articles will describe project progress and outcomes. As well, project experts will publish in reputable journals and deliver papers at relevant conferences to enhance project impact. Also, at least five position papers on the main results of the project will be published. White Papers will be written for policy purposes.

Planned policy briefs, topics, responsible partner and delivery time:

- Policy paper I. on digital forensics foresight (ZITIS - M12),
- Policy paper II. on ethical framework for cybercrime investing (CRI - M24),
- Policy paper III. on practitioners needs and requirements (CENTRIC – M36),
- Policy paper IV. on areas require more standardization (ASI – 48),
- Policy paper V. on practitioners needs and requirements – roadmap (PPHS – M54)

The articles and press media will be targeted at the target audience but also to other media channels (Table 7) that could maximize the reach. The following table shows a few examples of such news outlets, however the list is expected to grow in the process.:

Table 7 Few press agencies that can be used to maximise audience reach

Media	Country	Type
Reuters	Europe	Press Agency
Bloomberg	Europe	Press Agency
Agence France Presse	France	Press Agency
Athens News Agency	Greece	Press Agency

There is also a good opportunity to target the following European Commission channels:

- **Horizon Magazine** <http://horizonmagazine.eu/>
- **CORDIS website** <https://cordis.europa.eu/es>
- **DGHome Protection of public spaces newsletter**
https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/index.cfm?service_id=1410
- **Conferences and events** organised by the European Commission

6.1.8 Public deliverables

Due to the sensitivity of the subject, deliverables of the CYCLOPES project are mostly restricted for public view. However, some deliverables after a process of scrutiny and after they are accepted by the EC, will be published for the public and they are to be found on the EU platforms, such as CORDIS and many more, website downloads area, newsletter and so on. These documents are crucial and contain detailed descriptions of the results.

6.2 Collaborative events to further maximise impact

6.2.1 Practitioner workshops

Are the very engine of the project, organised as physical workshops, if the COVID situation allows, where practitioners' (i.e. LEAs) capabilities, gaps and requirements are identified, and common priorities towards innovations and standardisation are defined:

- Digital Forensics,
- Cybercrime as Affecting People,
- and Cybercrime as Affecting Systems.

A total of 15 workshops will be organized throughout the project lifespan, 3 each year. This task is highly relevant for practitioners (LEAs).

6.2.2 Annual Joint Live Exercises

The practitioner workshops provide data for the project's market and research watch, and the selected products and solutions identified by the market and research scans will be tested within annual Joint Live Exercises.

In addition to practitioners, relevant representatives of industry and academia will be invited to the exercises.

There are **5 total planned** joint live exercises and the purpose is to:

- Test the identified technology against a baseline of a representative scenario;
- Expose practitioners to new software and enable them to make a hands-on assessment outside of typical demos;
- Enable developers of technologies to receive direct feedback on how their solution addresses the gaps identified by practitioners and help them move to higher TRL solutions.

This task is highly relevant to the industry and SMEs.

6.2.3 Annual dissemination events

Will disseminate project findings for a large spectrum of stakeholders and ensure efficient interaction e.g. with industry and the academia. Moreover, these events will foster network activities, raise awareness of the project and bring together relevant practitioners and stakeholders who may wish to join to the CYCLOPES network and its activities.

- First dissemination event organized by PPHS in Poland or Brussels (M12);
- Second dissemination event organized by DITTS in The Netherlands (M24);
- Third dissemination event organized by UK Home Office in UK (M36);
- Fourth dissemination event organized by SPA in Sweden (M48);
- Fifth dissemination event organized by MUP in Croatia (M58)

The events will provide a platform to discuss the project's findings and specifically the recommendations for innovation uptake (incl. industrialisation) and standardisation. Moreover, Annual Workshops will foster network activities, raise awareness of the project and bring together relevant practitioners and stakeholders who may join the CYCLOPES network and its activities. The ultimate goal of such events is to bring sustainability to the project activities and increase relevant members in the network.

6.2.4 Annual standardisation workshops

Based on information gathered within task 4.2, CYCLOPES will choose at least one topic, which will be further elaborated during a dedicated yearly workshop. Workshops will be organised independently, or in cooperation with particular technical committees' workshops or conferences. The ambition is to promote standardisation as an effective tool in the fight against cybercrime, while exploring the opportunities to streamline processes and procedures that will maintain efficacy and maximise effectiveness.

These events could be organized at the same time with the dissemination events as there are similarities in both in terms of message and outreach.

6.2.5 External Events, Cooperation and Information Exchange:

CYCLOPES partners will also participate in **external events** (relevant conferences, seminars, workshops, fairs and other gatherings of experts, industry and academia) in order to present the project's goals and results to stakeholders, and obtain feedback that will allow CYCLOPES to maintain progress with the latest trends and conditions.

Outreach and clustering activities that aim to engage other interested consortia and RDI projects looking to strengthen resilience to cybercrime represent an important element of the project's dissemination plan. In this context, consortium partners are actively participating in the dissemination of research results. Through the active collaboration with other European consortia, new perspectives and visions for project success will emerge. Special attention will be set on alignment with EC's Community of Users events, so the outcomes of CYCLOPES can be exploited by the wider user community.

7 Communication Strategy

7.1 Visual materials

The visual identity is well defined by the project's logo (created at the time of the submission) and by the document templates (deliverables and standard PowerPoint- and Word document template provided at M1 by PPHS. These are provided as annexes at the end of document.

A promotional package was also created at M4 and will include:

- CYCLOPES Roll-up banners to be used during project events and events CYCLOPES partners will attend. These are also provided as digital and hard copies;
- CYCLOPES Leaflet to be disseminated during events in general, both in soft and hard copies;

It is being considered in the future adding maybe wearables or stationary supplies if this is seen as beneficial.

All communication materials, like the leaflets, roll-up, and any upcoming materials will be updated according to the needs of the consortium, and in order to update information according to project developments and successes.

7.1.1 Leaflet

The CYCLOPES Leaflet is designed in a similar fashion as the roll-up and the website. It is an A4 document that includes a brief description of the project, its objectives, funding, as well as a call to action that is added in order to invite potential network members to join the network and other stakeholders to provide their contributions (Annex III).

Two versions are offered; a smaller digital version and for print.

The current leaflet differs greatly from the content to its design compared to the one provided in the D6.11 Project branding. This was a necessary redesign in order to meet the project quality demands for a more informative and visually attractive set of marketing materials.

7.1.2 Roll-up

The CYCLOPES Roll-up is one of the main materials designed to catch the attention of potential audiences especially when the audience is able to physically or digitally see them.

Roll-ups serve as a first touch point with the project and paint the first impressions. Experience has taught us that they are the most effective when used while representing the project to varied audiences that are in crowd or passers-by, but also in keynote speeches, vlogs or video conferences.

As such, the Roll-up is designed to be minimalistic, representing the theme of the project via the chosen colour palette in line with the website and the logo. Furthermore, it includes contact details to invite further collaboration opportunities and contact information including social media (Annex II). Two versions are developed; the online version and the print. They differ slightly from one another. This was necessary due to its size for the writings to be readable on screen.

The current Roll-up differs greatly from the content to its design compared to the one provided in the D6.11 Project branding. This was a necessary redesign in order to meet the project quality demands for a more informative and visually attractive set of marketing materials.

7.2 Communication policy

The CYCLOPES project partners must be involved as much as possible in making dissemination materials especially presentations, flyers, blogs, newsletters, and press releases. Their contribution will be requested particularly in areas where they will have more opportunity for capacity building. All CYCLOPES beneficiaries will be potential contributors for WP6 dissemination.

Beyond the overall understanding, we may use the following internal protocols when planning to communicate externally in a form of online media tools.

7.2.1 Social media

All partners will update the WP6 Lead partner with quick updates of upcoming or past events and/or news related to the work they have completed/will be completed. WP6 lead partner will update the social media channels based on the information shared by the partners.

The lead partner will publish and maintain the social media tools based on their best knowledge and experience.

All partners should contribute to social media communication through their own organisational pages/feeds using relevant hashtags.

7.2.2 News, articles and press releases

Laurea will first modify and check the proposed dissemination material (e.g. press release) submitted in good time by the partner/beneficiary to allow for sufficient review and forward the material to the Coordinator.

The Coordinator will provide final validation of the material to be communicated externally through selected channels (e.g. website).

7.2.3 EU-Acknowledgement

All project dissemination and documentation materials should use the EU-funding acknowledgement in accordance with the grant agreement. This includes the sentence below and the EU-flag logo (Figure 9).

“This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Coordination and Support Action (2014-2020) under grant agreement No. 101021669”

Figure 7 EU acknowledgement flag and text

All sorts of external communication are encouraged to promote the CYCLOPES project and its results. The dissemination strategy of CYCLOPES is streamlined through this Dissemination Plan.

Provisions are made to provide coordination, consistency, and quality of publications for the benefit of the project's reputation. A second purpose is to give visibility within the project to any public relation activities of the partners.

Any evidence of a dissemination activity must be stored on the project repository (i.e. “Full Paper” version and presentation material).

In general, the dissemination activities, including but not restricted to publications and presentations shall be governed by Article 29 of the Grant Agreement. Specifically, partners will be responsible for including the EU emblem, acknowledgement of EU funding, and disclaimers.

7.2.4 Point of Contact for Dissemination and Communication

Each consortium partner assigns a dissemination and communication Point of Contact (POC), or preferably two persons, who will be responsible for dissemination and communication activities, as well as for social media liaison and requests.

The D&C PoC will ensure that the CYCLOPES Dissemination and Communication Plan is properly implemented and that the guidelines for dissemination and communication are respected and followed. In addition, the D&C PoC will monitor D&C activities.

7.2.5 Publication procedures

Given that the project is dealing with potential sensitive information there are a set of guidelines to follow in order to coordinate the participation of partners in dissemination activities and conferences (both in European and at international level) and properly notify the Commission of any event:

- It is essential that adequate time for considering the publication or participation in an event is given. Therefore, the notification may be circulated as soon as possible and no less than **30 days in advance** for publication of an event, **14 days in advance** for an event requiring online participation and at least **30 days in advance** for an event requiring physical participation.. The notification may be submitted to the coordinator and/or Dissemination Manager.
- The application may include, if possible, a copy of the conference program together with a rationale describing the conference and explaining the proposed role of CYCLOPES – i.e. networking, presentation of results, poster session, etc.
- Any partner in the consortium can publish its own results, it only needs to notify the dissemination manager and coordinator and fulfil the EC requirements hereafter

identified. It is however preferred that common publications arise as result of cooperation among the partners.

- Unless the Commission requests otherwise, any notice or publication by the contractors about the project, including at a conference or seminar, must specify that the project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme and may display the European Commission logo provided in Figure 9. When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence. A pre-print or an abstract of the paper, if digital format online, a link should be sent to the coordinator and dissemination manager.
- Any notice or publication by the partners, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, must specify a disclaimer that it reflects only the author’s view and that the project partners nor the European Commission are not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.
- If a result is shared by several partners, the publication needs the approval of all the partners involved. The notification submitted to the project coordinator will have to be circulated to all the partners involved. If there is no response, approval is granted.
- Participants may provide to the Coordinator and Dissemination Manager, a copy of the concise written report produced for the project within reasonable time unless a force majeure beyond the scope of the authors prevents this from happening.
- The attendee may provide, where possible, a copy of the conference proceedings or a suitable extract to the Coordinator.
- The provisions of the Contract and the Consortium Agreement should be taken into account in dissemination of results of the project.
- The cost and frequency of the conference attendance should always be minimised and kept in proportion to the size and resources of the Project.

7.2.6 Partners’ own press releases and other media contacts

All partners can send out press releases on their own. Partners willing to issue their own press releases must contact with the Dissemination Manager to make sure the effort is properly disseminated in the CYCLOPES channels.

For all other public project related communication, the use of the CYCLOPES logo and acknowledgement that the work was derived from the support of the project or the EC funding. When it comes to IPR, all publications must follow the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

7.2.7 Image rights

Notes on image quality and image rights needs to be paid attention at all publication activities. The general recommendation for the image quality is shown in the following Table 8. In the case of picture rights, the origin of the picture as well as the creator must be mentioned. During the project, the author is always responsible for obtaining appropriate image rights, whether for printing publications or web-based publications. The general recommendations are:

Table 8 Guidelines on the use of images in publications

Quality	<i>Images for publications in print, 300 dpi (Size 100 x 150mm) Images for web, 160 dpi (Size 60 x 60mm). Images should always be optimized for web. I.e. minify them from original sizes. If this is not done they will negatively impact the website load speed and SEO.</i>
Rights	© Institution/Company or author, origin

7.3 Crisis communication process and actions

The term Crisis is defined by the Cambridge Dictionary as “a time of great disagreement, confusion, or suffering” as well as “an extremely difficult or dangerous point in a situation”.

As every other organisation of people, a project can face a huge amount of confusing issues such as bad publicity, fake news and so on which might ask from its partners the correct way of communicating and disseminating the appropriate messages. To avoid any disagreements, it is seen as necessary to appoint a Crisis Manager (CM) for CYCLOPES. This is yet to be decided in the next WP leader meeting. A general protocol below in time of crisis is should be followed:

- Step 1: A crisis situation has been detected by a partner and communicated to the CM
- Step 2: CM and the coordinator assess together if the situation can be considered as a Crisis Situation
- Step 3: If this is not the case, the process will be stopped here.
- If this is the case, CM will have 1 week to work on the appropriate Crisis Plan to propose to the coordinator which will have 2 days to accept or not the Plan.
- Step 4: If the Crisis Plan is not accepted, the coordinator is in charge of making clear amendments to be transmitted to CM within 2 days. CM has 2 days to reply to them. The process cannot be longer than 10 days.
- If the Crisis Plan is accepted, it is immediately applied within CYCLOPES.

The above process naturally excludes a potential data breach where slightly more urgent corrective measures are required to be taken, normally within 48 hours.

Possible corrective measures include but are not limited to the following:

- Disallow further communication with the affected system by the public.
- Change all passwords and other relevant private data in case there are users involved.
- Investigate logs and audit the severity and potential data loss.
- Inform all participants of the data breach and further details within 72 hours.
- Apply corrective measures and patch vulnerabilities
- Prepare a public announcement.

8 Monitoring and assessment of dissemination and communication

Dissemination efforts will be measured using key performance indicators (KPIs) created based on the project objectives. The KPIs will be analysed and updated in each update of the DCP, if needed. The following table in Figure 9 shows the targets set forth for the successful implementation of D&C and reaching the intended impact of the project.

Project objectives:

OB1: To form a law enforcement agencies’ network across Europe, combating cybercrime

OB2: To define the capability gaps and requirements of practitioners fighting cybercrime

OB3: To monitor development of new technologies, research activities and innovations applied to combatting cybercrime

OB4: To indicate priorities regarding domains requiring standardisation and innovation uptake

OB5: To cooperate with other networks of practitioners and relevant stakeholders fighting cybercrime

OB6: Increase the visibility of the CYCLOPES network to enlarge its stakeholder community and maximise its impact

OB7: To analyse societal, ethical and legal challenges related to cybercrime

Table 9 CYCLOPES Dissemination and Communication KPIs

Target					
KPIs		Level of performance			Partners involved
D&C Tools	Definition of indicator	Poor	Good	Excellent	
Project Website	The number of visits	Less than 140 per month	140-300 per month	more than 300 per month	Responsible: LAU, PPHS. Contributing to content: All
	The number of page views	Less than 300 per month	300-500 per month	more than 500 per month	
	Average time spent on website	Less than 30 sec.	30 sec. – 1:30 min.	more than 1.5 min.	
Social Media	Followers on LinkedIn	Less than 50 per year	80 on yearly basis	More than 80 on yearly basis	Responsible: LAU, PPHS. Contributing partners: All
	Followers on Twitter	Less than 60 per year	90 on yearly basis	more than 90 on yearly basis	
	Number of posts	Less than 3 per month	3-7 per month	More than 7 per month	

Annual Joint Live Exercises	Number of practitioners per event	Less than 3 per event	20-25 per event	More than 25 per event	Responsible: SPA, (LAU, PPHS for D&C) Partners: PPHS, TNO, CENTRIC, ZITIS, UCD, CCI, all LEAs
	Number of participants from the scientific community per event	Less than 7 (online) Less than 5 (physical)	7-10 (online) 5-7(physical)	More than 10 (online) More than 7 (physical)	
	Number of participants from the Industry/SME per event	less than 2 per event	2-3 per event	More than 3per event	
Annual Dissemination Event	Number of participants per event	less than 70 per event	70-100 per event	more than 100 per event	D&C: LAU, PPHS Responsible: 1 st : PPHS 2 nd : DITTS 3 rd : UK Home 4 th : SPA 5 th : MUP Contributing: All partners
Annual Standardisation Workshop	Number of participants per event	less than 70 per event	70-100 per event	more than 100 per event	D&C: LAU, PPHS Responsible: ASI, Contributing: PPHS, ZITIS, all LEAs
Practitioner Workshops	Number of participants per workshop	Less than 10 (online) Less than 7 (physical)	10-15 (Online) 7-12 (physical)	More than 15 (online) More than 12 (physical)	D&C: LAU, PPHS Responsible: HO, (LAU, PPHS) Contributing: ZITIS, All LEAs except CPEB
Participation to External Events	Number of external events in which CYCLOPES participates	less than 5 per year	5-10 per year	more than 10 per year	D&C: LAU, PPHS Responsible partners: DITSS, Contributing partners: ALL
Liaison Activities and Synergies	Number of relevant projects/initiatives identified and contacted/invited at project events	Less than 4 on yearly basis	4-12 on yearly basis	more than 12 on yearly basis	Responsible: All D&C: LAU, PPHS

	Number of relevant organisations/ communities/experts identified and contacted/invited at project events	less than 12 on yearly basis	12-30 on a yearly basis	More than 30 on a yearly basis	
	Number of cooperation activities (common events and other clustering activities)	less than 1 on a yearly basis	2-3 on a yearly basis	more than 3 on a yearly basis	
Link to the Community of Users	Number of 'CYCLOPES' presentations made during plenary meetings and thematic workshops	1 per year	2 per year	more than 2 per year	Responsible: PPHS Contributing: ALL
Webinars	participants to the webinars	20-30 per webinar	30-50 per webinar	more than 50 per webinar	Responsible: DITSS Contributing: PPHS, IANUS, ZITIS, LAU, SPA, CPEB
Bi-Annual Newsletters	Newsletters published	Less than 2 per year	2 per year	more than 2 per year	Responsible: LAU Participating partners: All
	Subscribers	20-50	50-100	more than 100	
CYCLOPES Community of Users	Number of new members (organisations not individuals)	0-10 per year	10-20 per year	more than 20 per year	All

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ANNEX I Glossary of Terms

Term	Definition/description
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EP	Exploitation Plan
PM	Project Manager
WP	Work Package
PC	Project Coordinator
QM	Quality Manager
CM	Crisis Manager
EC	European Commission
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
EU	European Union
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency

ANNEX II Roll-up

CYCLOPES

**CYBERCRIME
LAW ENFORCEMENT
PRACTITIONERS' NETWORK**
An innovation-driven network of LEAs
combating cybercrime

**YOUR HELP IS NEEDED, PLEASE
GET IN TOUCH!**

WE INVITE CONTRIBUTIONS FROM
LEAs , SMEs (industry) & RESEARCH (academia)

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Annex III CYCLOPES Leaflet

CYBERCRIME LAW ENFORCEMENT PRACTITIONERS' NETWORK

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THE PROJECT

The CYCLOPES project builds and maintains an innovation-driven network of law enforcement agencies (LEAs) combating cybercrime. We identify solutions and research activities that help tackle the complexity of cybercrime – whilst eliciting priorities for standardisation and recommendations for innovation implementation and increased uptake.

CYCLOPES increases impact by creating successful synergies with (LEAs), Industry and Academia. This is achieved through interactive Joint Live Exercises and stimulating dialogue on pressing security matters and crime concerns in relevant workshops, webinars and events.

OBJECTIVES

- To form a law enforcement agencies' network across Europe, combating cybercrime
- To define the capability gaps and requirements of practitioners fighting cybercrime
- To monitor the development of new technologies, research activities and innovations applied to combating cybercrime
- To indicate priorities regarding domains requiring standardisation and innovation uptake
- To cooperate with other networks of practitioners and relevant stakeholders fighting cybercrime
- Increase the visibility of the CYCLOPES network to enlarge its stakeholder community and maximise its impact
- To analyse societal, ethical and legal challenges related to cybercrime

KEY PARTNERS & NETWORKS

CYCLOPES amplifies the outputs of other relevant organisations and networks – complementing their activities rather than duplicating efforts. The results and achievements will act as a springboard for future actions that harmonise, where possible, with existing networks and organisations also striving to aid the fight against cybercrime in Europe. Key partners and networks for CYCLOPES includes:

IDENTIFYING GAPS, NEEDS AND CAPABILITIES

Every year, 3 workshops will be organised with each workshop dedicated to different domains fighting cybercrime: 1) Cybercrimes affecting people directly; 2) Cybercrimes affecting systems; 3) Digital forensics. The graphic below illustrates the planned topics for the year 2021. At the end of each year, new topics for each domain will be chosen.

Latest trends and threats, plus input from external stakeholders (WPS)

- Exploitation of 5G networks
- Cyberstalking and cyberbullying
- Illegal trade on the darknet
- Cryptocurrencies
- Cyberattacks on networks
- IoT - Smart Homes
- Autonomous/Smart Transport
- Adverse use of AI
- Use of social engineering
- ...

Thematic topics highlighted yearly and reviewed by domain leads

Year	Practitioner Workshops		
	Cybercrime – Affecting People Directly	Cybercrime – Affecting Systems	Digital Forensics
2021	Combating child sexual exploitation	Malware & malicious software	Mobile phones / wearables
2022			
2023			
2024			
2025			

Using a prioritisation technique, the thematic topics are assessed annually and planned for the coming 12 months. The topics not completed in that year will be included in the review for the following year

LEAs - JOIN THE NETWORK ACADEMIA AND INDUSTRY - SUBMIT YOUR SOLUTION

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Public

42

ANNEX IV CYCLOPES Logo

ANNEX V Colour Codes

HEX	/	RGB
#edcd4f		237, 205, 79
#05347e		5, 52, 126

ANNEX VI PowerPoint Template

ANNEX VII Deliverable Template

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable x.x <title>
<Dissemination level>

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DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable reference number	Dx.x
Deliverable name	
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public/Confidential/EU restricted
Work package contributing to the deliverable	WP1
Due date	
Version	
Actual submission date	<Filled in by the Coordinator>
Responsible organisation	
Editor(s)	
Contributor(s)	
Reviewer(s)	
Disclaimer	

DOCUMENT CHANGE CONTROL

Version	Date	Status	Author(s), reviewer	Description
0.1	DD/MM/YY	Draft		Initial Draft
0.3	DD/MM/YY	Draft		Review
0.4	DD/MM/YY	Draft		Final review
1.0	DD/MM/YY	Final		Final approval and submission

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Summary

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Introduction

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Subheading 1

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Subheading 2

"Sed ut perspiciatis unde omnis iste natus error sit voluptatem accusantium doloremque laudantium, totam rem aperiam, eaque ipsa quae ab illo inventore veritatis et quasi architecto beatae vitae dicta sunt explicabo."

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Table 1 & table example

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Conclusion
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